

Understanding users:

A comparative study about informing designers by different sources of information

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Abstract: This paper describes a comparative study, which explores the influence of different sources of information on design sessions aiming for product concepts for children with autism. Six design teams were informed about autistic children under three conditions: (A-teams) only literature, (B-teams) literature + direct contact, (C-teams) literature + video. In a one-hour session, each team conducted a discussion, brainstormed ideas, and developed one concept design. The sessions were videotaped, transcribed, and analyzed for signs of empathy. The proposed product concepts were evaluated by parents and teachers of the children. Results show that the two B-teams discussed the user group most intensively, and produced concepts that fitted the user group best. The two A-teams made many false assumptions about the user group. One C-team discussed the user group intensively and produced a product concept appreciated by caregivers, while the other C-team did the opposite. The latter team was not motivated for the session. The findings underline that, and show examples of how, direct contact, willingness and motivation of designers are key-factors in empathic design.

Key words: *empathy, information sources, direct contact, ideation*

1. Introduction

In user-centered design, there is a broad consensus that designers should be informed about their user group [e.g., 1-4]. However, little is known about the way in which this informing can or should take place. Designers can learn from different sources of information. For example, designers can meet (prospective) users themselves or build on the insights of others, by reading literature of experts, or studying field research reports (e.g., personas or video) [11]. If designers meet users themselves, they are actively involved in the process of data gathering and sense making. However, connecting observations from direct contact with users to a body of theory about a specific user group can be difficult. For example, when designers meet two or three children with autism, they might consider the observed behaviour, skills, and preferences of these specific children applicable to the whole autistic spectrum. On the contrary, building on the insights of others without any contact with these children can be difficult as well, because designers cannot anchor this information to own experience.

In this study, we explored how different sources of information influence (1) design teams' understanding of users and (2) the quality of the product concepts that they produce. This paper aims to provide more insight into the effects of different sources of information on designers and their design process.

2. Empathic design

In empathic design, designers attempt to get closer to the lives and experiences of users, aiming to increase the likelihood that products and services fit the users and enhance their lives [2]. In design literature, McDonagh [6] defines empathy as the intuitive ability to identify with other people's thoughts and feelings- their motivations, emotional and mental models, values, priorities, preferences, and inner conflicts. Empathy is an individual ability, varying in strength over time and from one person to the other. However, a designer's empathy level is not only defined by ability. Also a designer's willingness and motivation to obtain empathy for users plays a part [3]. For example, a designer who has a personal connection with the user group or a strong commitment to the project is more willing to gain empathy with users.

2.1. Empathic design techniques

Kouprie and Sleeswijk Visser [3] report three main classes of techniques to enhance empathy in design. First, designers can obtain *empathy through direct contact* with users (e.g., observation, interviews, participation in their activities). The designers see through their own eyes the users' situation, condition, behaviours, feelings, and needs. Many design researchers state their conviction that direct contact is a prime and irreplaceable source for obtaining empathy with users [e.g., 1-2, 4-5, 9]. Still, systematic or controlled comparison studies have not been reported. Second, designers can obtain *empathy through communication* by a third party. User researchers use special *communication* tools to convey the stories of users to the designers. (e.g., using personas, literature, videos, transcripts). Third, designers can obtain *empathy through imagination*. The designer steps into parts of the users' experience by simulating the users' condition (e.g., performing role-playing, experience prototyping).

In our study, we used the techniques '*empathy through direct contact*' and '*empathy through communication*' as sources of information for the design teams. We left out '*empathy through imagination*', because this technique does not involve 'real user' involvement, and can be used with either of the other techniques during idea generation and concept development.

2.2. An empathic challenge: Children with autism

The user group in our study is children with a disorder in the spectrum of autism. Autism is an inborn developmental disorder that affects around 1 in 1000 of the population. Affected children may display a range of disabilities at many levels, such as impairment in social relationships, communication, and imagination [12]. The official term is 'autism spectrum disorder'. The term 'spectrum disorder' indicates the great variety in ability, needs, and preferences. In this paper, we refer to "children with autism" for short. Most of the children cannot read, write, or speak language. For designers, this user group is an empathic challenge: the experiential world of these children is radically different from children with 'normal' development [10]. With this extreme user group, we expect signs of misunderstanding in the designers' discussions and the designs they produce. Literature about autism is available, but much of it is rather theoretical, and does not paint a rich picture of life as is deemed conducive to empathy. In this paper, we explore how to support designers in a fruitful way in learning about children with autism.

3. Comparative study: Informing design teams under three conditions

This study explored how different sources of information influence design teams' (1) understanding of users and (2) quality of product concepts. Design teams developed product concepts for children with autism in design sessions. As preparation, the teams were informed about their user group under three conditions. In order to determine the teams' level of empathy with autistic children, we analyzed the teams' discourse during their sessions (see paragraph 3.1). In order to evaluate the quality of the proposed concepts, we asked caregivers of children with autism to evaluate the teams' concepts. As no other, caregivers can provide expert judgements on how well product concepts fit the experiential worlds of these children (see paragraph 3.2). Figure 1 depicts an overview of the study.

Figure.1 Structure of the study, showing teams, conditions, and process.

We expected that the B-teams obtain more empathy for the user group, and design product concepts that fit the user group better than the A- and C-teams. Also, we expected that the C-teams obtain more empathy and design better product concepts than the A-teams, because video conveys more facets about the users' experiences than what can be described in literature. For instance, an abstract notion as 'the child with autism is easily distracted by sensory stimuli' gets empathic meaning when you can see (or witness) what level of stimulation it was, how distracted the child was, and how difficult it was to regain its attention.

3.1 Evaluation of the design sessions

For each condition, two design teams performed a one-hour session in which they designed a concept for a lunch product for children with autism (see Figure 2.). The teams consisted of two or three international M.Sc. design students of the faculty of Industrial Design Engineering (Delft University of Technology) who volunteered for the study.

Figure.2 A design team in their session

Procedure

The teams were informed about their user group under three conditions (A, B, and C). The actual session was similar in setup for all teams, as can be seen in Figure 1.

One week before the sessions, the facilitator emailed the designers to inform them about their user group and provided them literature about autism. This was a 4-paged text document from the website of the UK National Autism Society [14]. This text contained an explanation and characteristics of autism, such as difficulty with social communication, social interaction, and social imagination; it also described examples of these difficulties. The teams did not yet receive their design assignment to prevent them from thinking ahead about design solutions. The designers were instructed to only use information provided by the facilitator to ensure each participant was informed as planned.

Teams A1 and A2 did not receive any extra information (condition A: literature only). The B and C teams received more information about the user three days before the session. Teams B1 and B2 conducted 30-minute observations of five autistic children at school (condition B: literature + direct contact). Team B1 observed the children in a language lesson. Team B2 observed the children during the activity of eating fruit. The teams observed different activities for practical reasons; only one team could be present in the classroom at a time. They could take notes, ask questions to teachers, and discuss their observations afterwards on their way back. Team C1 and C2 watched videos of these 30-minute observations (condition C: literature + video). Team C1 watched team B1's video of the language lesson. Team C2 watched team B2's video of eating fruit.

In a one-hour session, each team designed a product concept for children with autism. First, the facilitator instructed the team to design a lunch product for children with autism, fitting their needs and preferences (5 minutes). Then, in the discuss-phase, the team could discuss their user data together (10 minutes). Next, in the brainstorm-phase, the facilitator invited the team to start generate, select, and elaborate ideas into a final concept (35 minutes). Finally, the team presented their concept to the facilitator (10 minutes). All sessions were videotaped, transcribed and analyzed. The amount of time spent on discussing the user group was taken as indicator of empathy, because direct measurements of empathy are difficult [3].

Results

The results show that the B-teams discussed the user group most often, followed by C-, then A-teams. The A-teams referred more to the literature, devoted more time to generating ideas, and produced more ideas than the B- and C-teams. The A-teams only discussed the user group in the discuss-phase of the session. The literature played a minor role in the B- and C-teams' discussions. The B-teams discussed the user group even in the brainstorm-phase. The two C-teams differed from each other. Team C1 hardly discussed the user group, while team C2 did, even in the brainstorm-phase. Team C1 generated ideas most of the time, while team C2 did not. This section describes the course of each session. Figures 3 to 5 show graphs for each session, representing roughly how often the designers discuss the user group over time (based on counting explicit references in the transcripts by two of the researchers).

Team A1

In the discuss-phase, team A1 discussed children with autism in general. The team already started thinking about solutions, before the facilitator's instruction to start ideation. In the brainstorm-phase, the designers made wrong assumptions about the user group. For example, a designer said: "I think they always go to normal schools". Another designer had an idea about a timer for their lunchbox: "This helps not to forget their lunch". Even though a timer on itself could be a good idea for these children, you would not use this as an argument if you had observed the structured day of these children. Finally, a designer referred to a film about amnesia and said: "I thought autistic people have memory problems". The team largely based their ideas on their own imagination and not on the provided literature.

Figure. 3 An impression of the amount of discussion in time during the sessions of team A1 and A2.

Team A2

Coincidentally, one of the three designers in team A2 had a far acquaintance that had an autistic child. Therefore, team A2's condition is somewhat similar to that of the B- or C-teams. In the discuss-phase, this designer added real life examples of this child to the characteristics of the user group in the literature. However, the team was uncertain about the characteristics. For example, one designer wondered: "Do they have any physical disabilities?" In the brainstorm-phase, the designer with experience based her ideas on contact with the child, while the other two designers based their ideas on their imagination and the literature.

Team B1

In the discuss-phase, team B1 discussed their observations about the children and the teachers from the school visit. Also, they mentioned the literature three times. Even during the brainstorm-phase, they kept referring to their visit. The team thought of their own childhood to come up with ideas for the kind of food that can be put in their lunchbox. In developing ideas, they involved findings from their observations, such as the children learning to speak, routines, the use of pictograms, and rewards given by teachers. The ideas were based on the observation.

Figure. 3 An impression of the amount of discussion in time during the sessions of team B1 and B2.

Team B2

In the discuss-phase, team B2 never referred to the literature. They discussed all the children and teachers they met at the school, and based their ideas on their observations. In the brainstorm-phase, they discussed the scenario of use intensively. They did not know and could not reach agreement on whether the children would carry their own lunch to school or whether a parent or teacher does this. They needed more information and decided (for now) that the children would carry the lunchbox themselves.

Team C1

In the discuss-phase, team C1 referred to children with autism in general. They did not discuss the children they observed in the video. They already started thinking about solutions, before the facilitator's instruction to start ideation. In the brainstorm-phase, they struggled to come up with ideas; the facilitator mentioned this team was not that motivated during their session. The latter part of the brainstorm-phase, they had most of their ideas. As with teams A, their ideas were based on their imagination and experience with 'normal' children.

Figure. 5 An impression of the discussion about users in time during the sessions of team C1 and C2.

Team C2

In the discuss-phase, team C2 discussed the characteristics of each child and teacher they observed in the video. They referred two times to the literature. Their discussion about the user group continued in the brainstorm-phase. Their ideas were based on findings from the video and literature. They often referred to the activity of eating of fruit, because this was observed in the video. The first part of the brainstorm-phase, they discussed design criteria for the children and teachers. The latter part they detailed their concept.

Discussion

The findings confirm our expectations of which conditions produce the most fruitful discussions about the users. In decreasing order: (B) visiting them, (C) watching a video, and (A) reading literature. The B-teams were actively learning about the user group and had a common ground for discussion. They gathered information with their team in the situation and could share and discuss observations during the 30-minute bus trip back home. Interestingly, the B- and C-teams considered caregivers as part of the context of product use, while the A-teams did not mention caregivers at all.

The B- and C-teams hardly referred to the literature in their discussions. Observing the user group in a real situation or on video produces more empathy than merely reading literature. The A-teams discussed the children in general and started early thinking about solutions. They easily made (wrong) assumptions to start ideation. Apparently, they automatically filled in their knowledge gap to continue their session. Interestingly, the B-teams who met the children had more problems with making assumptions quickly. They wanted to get the details right. For example, team B2 discussed a long time about who would carry the lunchbox to school.

3.2. Part 2: Evaluation of the concepts

To assess which team produced better fitting designs, five caregivers of children with autism, being three mothers, one speech therapist and one teacher, were asked to evaluate the six concepts. Caregivers are experienced with these children, and therefore can provide expert judgements on how well product concepts fit the experiential worlds of the user group. An independent illustrator made drawings of the six concepts to visually elaborate them all to the same level, preventing variation of drawing skills between the teams to influence the evaluation. The designs are shown in Figure 6.

Procedure

Caregivers blind-reviewed the six product concepts by means of a questionnaire, in which for each concept they were instructed to study the drawing, the description and the argumentation of the design team. Next, they rated ('yes', 'a little', 'no') to what degree the concept fits the needs and preferences of children with autism, and motivated their choice. Finally, they chose one concept that fitted the user group best.

Results

In general, the caregivers said that the concepts of the B-teams fitted the user group better than those of the A- and C-teams. In fact, they said the concepts of the A-teams did not fit at all. The concepts of the C-teams got mixed reviews. Below we discuss each of these.

Team A1: A lunchbox with a help screen

The team had motivated their concept as *"Our lunchbox is just a lunchbox, because children with autism want to feel as normal people"*. The therapist reacted negatively on this statement: *"I don't think they feel as normal people. Moreover, a screen doesn't work, because they have difficulties doing two things at the same time, such as eating and watching TV"*. Also the teacher thought this concept does not fit the children. One mother said this concept fits her child a little: *"I think it's good for play, but not for eating. It would distract him from eating. Showing an example of how to play with a toy could be a good idea."* Another mother similarly pointed out that learning while eating is too distracting.

Team A2: Boxes in a lunchbox for clarity

Although one designer had prior experience on autism, the therapist and teacher rated this concept negatively. The therapist motivated: *"This box is so interesting that it becomes play material. For some children, eating is impossible like this. However, filling the boxes together with a caregiver and putting them in a big box is fun and educational. I can imagine this can be used for other activities than eating a meal"*. One mother said this concept fits her child a little bit: *"My son likes to eat food separately. For example, he eats meat separate from potatoes. This gives a feeling of control and safety. I like the screen to make a private space; I can imagine they like this. But separate boxes distract my child too much. He can put them in a row or build a tower without actually eating"*. One mother explained it is too complicated: *"For many children this would be too chaotic, too many options, but I do like the screen for a quite place."* One mother rated the concept positively: *"The screen is nice, and they can practise choosing. Often children with autism have difficulties choosing something"*. Interestingly, the screen was the idea of the designer with prior experience on autism.

1: A lunchbox with a help screen (Team A1)

The lunchbox has a screen on both the inside as the outside, aiming to show the children how to eat.

2: Boxes in a lunchbox for clarity (Team A2)

The lunchbox can be filled with little boxes for each type of food to make rules between parent and child about the content.

3: A layered lunchbox (Team B1)

The lunchbox has a separate layer for each snack moment. The top layer lights up when it is time to eat. After eating, the layer goes to the bottom.

4: Match to open the lunchbox (Team B2)

Children can open the lunchbox by matching the right icons to the icons on the box.

5: A social lunchbox (Team C1)

This lunchbox makes lunch a social activity. When all lunchboxes are linked, they change colour to indicate it is time to eat.

6: Attention to the food! (Team C2)

This lunchbox aims to help the children keep their attention to eating by reminding them each time they are distracted.

Figure.6 Drawings and descriptions of the six product concepts, used to evaluate with mothers and teachers.

Team B1: A layered lunchbox

Unanimously, all caregivers chose this concept as best fit with the user group. One mother explained: *“This lunchbox is most effective for eating lunch. It’s important that a child can eat independently in an easy way. As parent you can determine yourself how you can best use it for your child, because each child is different”*. The therapist said: *“This lunchbox is very practical and well structured, visual and tactual. The lunchbox indicates the order and enlarges the independence of the children. In the morning, they can take out all their food at once, instead of one by one. This saves time and provides more independence.”* The teacher agrees: *“Working downwards is a good idea, just as the pictograms on top of the box. I would match them with the ones on the plan-board.”*

Team B2: Match to open the lunchbox

Three caregivers said this concept fits the user group, while the other two caregivers said it fits a little. The teacher thought the idea is good: *“It is concrete and visual. Many children enjoy puzzling.”* A mother agreed: *“It looks nice, and it is a little game to invite to lunch. It is important to change the pictograms regularly to keep the box interesting”*. The other mother motivated: *“The lunchbox is challenging and elicits moments for language and asking for help. However, the teacher did not agree: “Many children experience soft material as unpleasant. This could have negative effect on eating. Moreover, this lunchbox aims children to learn, while eating itself can be challenging enough. Therefore, relaxation should be most important, not learning”*. Finally, one mother rated the concept with ‘a little’: *“I would adjust the pictures to the content of the lunchbox. I would add for example the sound ‘enjoy your meal’. So, they learn to say that”*.

Team C1: A social lunchbox

Some caregivers disliked this idea, because the children will not understand and enjoy the social aspect. One mother said: *“Children with autism do not want to be social. They do not like others to be near their food”*. According to the therapist and a mother this concept showed some promising elements. The mother said: *“I like the separate compartments for food; this will work. Linking boxes won’t. The children dislike sharing food. If my son is eating, I would never stimulate sharing, because my child should feel safe. I do like the idea of a sound when it’s time to eat. I think the teacher would set this time”*. The therapist liked the idea of linking: *“Through linking the boxes, the children come close to each other. Sharing food is not practical. A sound to announce lunchtime can result in a lot of commotion”*. On the contrary, one mother liked the concept, because it stimulates their weaknesses. She explained: *“The lunchbox seems technological, and this will interest the technicians among the autists. Linking supports the feeling of togetherness, although it can frighten a child to be connected to someone else. This should be introduced well. The sound can be fun, but disturbing for others”*.

Team C2: Attention to the food!

Three caregivers rated this concept positively. For example, the therapist said: *“Indeed, we have to remind children over and over when they are eating. The children will focus at the lights in the fork, which might cause them to pinch their fork all the time. It would be great if lights turn on when they put something in their mouth. However, the risk might be they put too much at a time in their mouth. Some of my children already do this”*. A mother said: *“I like the concept. I have to tell my son over and over he should take a bite. I like the fork, but it*

should not be too much fun, because that distracts from eating. Pinching the fork with a light is nice too, even though I wonder if the light stays off when that compartment is empty". Another mother agrees: "I like to give my child something to play with that causes lights or sound. Especially when he hears something like 'eat this sandwich'". Finally, the teacher and another mother said the concept fits a little. The mother wrote: "This would only fit children who are quickly distracted".

Discussion

The results of the evaluations on the product concepts corresponded to what we expected regarding to the helpfulness of the sources of information, in decreasing order: (B) visiting them, (C) watching a video, and (A) reading literature. Especially, the A-teams made many wrong assumptions resulting in product concepts that do not fit the user group. These teams were not aware of the limitations of their user group. Therefore, they used their own imagination leading to extreme ideas. They were not led by existing solutions for the user group, such as the use of pictograms to structure the child's day. The ideas of the B-teams were related directly to their observations. For example, one designer mentioned the lunchbox should say the name of the food each time a child picks something out of it. He based this on the observation that the teacher kept repeating the word *'banana'* when the boy ate his banana. The B-teams discussed and detailed the product in such a way, that it would fit the children they observed in the classroom. Teams B1 and C1 observed a language lesson, while team B2 and C2 observed the activity of eating fruit. Interestingly, these two different subjects had different effects on the session: generalizing and particular, respectively. Observing the language lesson resulted in ideas about educational lunchboxes, while observing the children eating fruit resulted in ideas about lunchboxes that support eating. According to the caregivers, the product concepts of team B2 and C2 better fit the user group than the concepts of team B1 and C1. They did not appreciate the educational lunchboxes that much, because they think eating is difficult enough already. The designers who observed the children eating fruit realized this.

4. General discussion

As the results show, direct contact brings most inspiring and lively discussion about the user group within the design teams and leads to product concepts fitting the user group's needs and preferences. However, in design practice, direct contact between designers and users is often impossible, because it requires a much higher investment in terms of time, effort, and budget. One solution would be that user researchers use communication techniques to bring the experiences of a user group vividly to designers [11]. This study shows that direct contact is the best way for designers to learn about and design for this specific user group, and that merely viewing the observations on video is not enough. Therefore, we propose that designers should make an effort to meet with real users at least once, even if time and budget are limited. Of course, designers should not solely learn from direct contact with users, because they would miss out the admirable body of theory on autism available in science and other sources of information, such as the Internet, documentaries, and books. The strength lies in integrating different sources of information. Personal experience helps designers to understand the theory on autism and vice versa. Designers should integrate different sources of information to reach any level of empathy with this user group.

Although the study did not reject our expectations, we learned new nuances of the subject. For example, the level of understanding and quality of product concepts depended on the designer's skills, willingness, and prior experiences. These variables are difficult to quantify. Of course, skills or prior experience could not be influenced and we did not select designers on these qualities, but willingness to empathize with users appeared to differ for the three conditions.

We noticed differences between the six different sessions in atmosphere and the designers' attitude. Visiting the school made the designers apparently function better as a team. The designers in the B-teams had a shared experience: they observed the same activity, in the same room, with the same children. Moreover, in practice, these designers would be already willing to learn, because they took the time and effort to learn about their users. The B-teams were visibly more motivated during the session than the A-teams.

Video showed to have great value in bringing empathy to design teams. Designers who had contact with users can use video to keep their observations alive during their design process. Moreover, video can help designers in communicating their insights to others, as long as these are willing and motivated to learn about their users. Still, the level of involvement will be larger: A designer recording the video during observation is actively involved in the data collection. A designer who merely watches the video can also take a more passive role. This was clearly visible in the two C-teams. Team C1 was less motivated than team C2. This lack of motivation of team C1 might be due to the fact that the children were not that active in the video of the language lesson. Moreover, the camera was pointed at the teacher who taught the children the difference between 'warm' and 'cold'. The design team could not clearly see the children's reactions to this lesson. In contrast, the video of team C2 showed the children in their activity of eating fruit. In this activity the children were active. So, seeing the children in active behaviour seems to relate to the motivation and willingness of the designers as well.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we described our findings of a study in which we explored how the way of informing a design team influences their understanding of a user group and the quality of product concepts that they produce. Compared to informing designers by video or literature, direct contact with users brings most empathy and leads to product concepts fitting the users needs and preferences best. Also video can bring empathy to design, as long as designers are willing and motivated to learn about users. This willingness and motivation appear to be key-factors for empathy, automatically stimulated by direct contact.

Unfortunately, direct contact typically requires a much higher investment in terms of time, effort, and budget. When this is not available, communication techniques, such as video can support a design team, provided designers are stimulated for motivation and willingness.

In further research, we explore the role of direct contact in a design process, and how this contact can be effectively brought to understanding and used in a design project [9].

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